
ANALYSIS OF JADITH, ITS PURPOSE AND ACTIVITY

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Abstract: This article describes the origin, development, main ideas and goals of Jadidism in the regions of Turkestan, Caucasus, Crimea, and Tatarstan at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century.

Key words: Jadidism, Turkestan, education, madrasa and schools.

Jadidchilik (Arabic, jadid - new) is a socio-political, educational movement that gained significant importance in the life of Turkestan, Caucasus, Crimea, and Tatarstan at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. Jadidism first arose in the 80s of the 19th century in the Crimea under the leadership of Ismailbek Gasprinsky among the Crimean Tatars. The representatives of the Jadid movement often called themselves progressives, and later Jadids.

The advanced progressive forces of that time, first of all, the intellectuals, felt that the local population was lagging behind the global development and realized the need to reform the society. Jadidism was essentially a political movement. It has periods of formation and defeat, which can be conditionally divided into four. In Turkestan, Bukhara and Khiva, these periods are 1895-1905; 1906-16; 1917-20; Includes the years 1921-29.

In the first period, Tsarist Russia was firmly established in Turkestan. With the help of his political agents (representatives), he not only limits the powers of local khans and emirs, but turns them into puppets, creates conditions for the work and living of Russian and Western investors, and looks after the interests of various companies and joint-stock companies. At the same time, the demands and needs of the local population were not taken into account, disregard for their religious beliefs, customs, and their disdain increased. Judges with a high life and scientific level were replaced by inexperienced people, bribery and social-political injustice escalated. Restrictions on the activities of madrassas and schools, replacing local place names with Russian terms, even going as far as putting crosses on the necks of judges during the court proceedings, such cases of humiliation of the local population clearly showed the indolence of the colonialists. The situation of that time was well described by Muhammadal Khalfa Sabir Oglu (Dukchi Eshon) in his “Address” (1898) to the people.

Progressive forces thinking about the nation's perspective existed among almost all classes of people - artisans, farmers, merchants, landowners, scholars. The

intellectuals initially decided to start the struggle against tsarism on the political and educational front, awakening the people from the age-old backwardness. The Jadidism movement found a favorable ground for its development in the Turkestan region under such historical conditions.

Advanced scientists, modern experts in the fields of industry and agriculture, cultural figures have grown up from among the ancestors, they dreamed of seeing the country prosperous and the Motherland independent, and they fought selflessly on this path.

In the struggle of the Jadids for the independence of Turkestan, the following directions were mainly prioritized:

expanding the network of new method schools; sending talented young people to study abroad;

creation of various educational societies and theater troupes;

building a national democratic state in Turkestan by publishing newspapers and magazines, raising the socio-political consciousness of the people. These things could be done only if a strong party of Jadid intellectuals was formed.

The main ideas and goals of Jadidlik were:

To liberate Turkestan from medieval backwardness and religious superstition, Sharia reform,

spreading enlightenment to the people,

The struggle to establish an autonomous government in Turkestan,

To build a free and prosperous society by establishing a constitutional monarchy and parliament in Bukhara and Khiva, and later a democratic republic,

introducing a stable national currency and creating a national army.

In Tashkent, Fergana, Bukhara, Samarkand and Khiva, Jadidchilik movement was formed from cultural and educational societies and associations opened by some groups of free-thinking and progressive people [1].

Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abduqadir Shukuri (Shakuri), Saidahmad Siddiqi-Ajziy (Samarkand), Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdulla Avloni, Ubaidulla Asadullakhojaev (Ubaydulla Khojaev), Tashpolatbek Norbotabekov (Tashkent) are among the founders of the Jadid movement in Turkestan.), Fitrat, Faizulla Khojaev, Usmonkhoja Polathojaev, Abdulvahid Burhanov, Sadriddin Ainiy, Abdulkadir Muhiddinov (Bukhara), Obidjon Mahmudov, Hamza, Cholpon, Ishakkhan Ibrat, Muqammadsharif Sofizoda (Fergana Valley), Polvonniyoz Haji Yusupov, Bobohun Salimov (Khorazm) lived.

Jadidism in the Turkestan region is divided into three according to the place and direction of its spread: Jadidism of Turkestan, Bukhara and Khiva. There are some differences between the Jadids of Turkestan and the Jadids of Bukhara and Khiva. Intellectuals formed the social basis of modernism in Turkestan. They stood at the

forefront of the struggle against the colonialism of tsarist Russia and advocated the first autonomous and then independent state of Turkestan, which was turned into a source of raw materials for tsarism.

Jadidism in Bukhara took place in difficult socio-political conditions compared to Turkestan. Its composition consisted mainly of the progressive part of the urban population of Bukhara: intellectuals, mullahs, small shopkeepers and administrators, artisans, merchants. At first, the influence of Jadids among peasants and soldiers was low.

Jadids came up with a number of demands in the field of economy and management, for example, tax reduction. At first, they wanted to introduce reforms within the framework of the emirate system in Bukhara. In Bukhara, a farmer from Vobkent, Joraboy, opened the first new method school.

The modernist movement in Bukhara was opposed by some ignorant mullahs, a stream of ancients who were enemies of any innovations and reforms. At the beginning of the 20th century, Bukhara society was divided into 2 groups: the progressives led by Ikram Domla and the ancients led by Mulla Abdurazzaq. In 1908, “Bukharai Sharif Company” was established and engaged in publishing textbooks and selling books. Ahmadjon Hamdiy (Abusaidov), Usmankhoja Polathojaev (Usman Khoja), Hamidkhoja Mehriy, Abdulvahid Burkhanov, Abdulkadir Muhiddinov, Sadriddin Ainiy, Abdurahman Saadiy were the organizers of the company. In December 1909, Jadids founded the secret society “Tarbiyai atfol” (“Children’s Education”) in Bukhara (founders: Abdulvahid Burkhanov, Hamidkhoja Mehriy, Ahmadjon Hamdiy, Mukammil Burkhanov, Haji Rafe). This society sent young people from Turkestan and Bukhara to study at the department of “Bukhara Educational Educational Society” in Istanbul. Education abroad has made a radical change in the outlook of young people [2].

Although Jadidism started in Bukhara and Turkestan at the same time, the difficult environment in the emirate accelerated its development. From 1910, the Jadidchilik movement took an organizational form in Bukhara, and a party was formed on the basis of the secret society “Tarbiyai atfol” (see Young Bukharas).

Modernism, which was formed in Khiva at the beginning of the 20th century, came into existence under somewhat different historical conditions. It mainly consisted of two streams here. His right-wing movement united the owners of trade and industrial enterprises developing in the khanate and representatives of the rich. Islamkhoja, the prime minister of Khiva Khan Asfandiyar Khan, led this movement.

The right-wing current of Jadidism aimed to open a wide path for the development of free market relations by carrying out socio-economic reforms while preserving the power of the khan in the country. In Khiva, the left movement of Jadidchilik united small investors, artisans and representatives of different classes of

the people, and the leader of it was Bobohun Salimov. They set the goal of increasing the political activity of the people by establishing new method schools in Khiva Khanate.

In 1904, the “community of charity” was established, and with its support, the first new Methodist school was opened in the city of Khiva (November 10, 1904). Khiva’s Jadids were not content with educational activities, but also fought against the khan system. Until the First World War, Khiva did not have a single center and program documents. However, the Jadidchilik movement became a major socio-political force in the Khiva Khanate, and in August 1914 it took the form of a party (see Young Khivakers).

The Russo-Japanese War of 1904-1905, the 1st Russian Revolution of 1905-1907, the Iranian Revolution of 1905-1911, and the Young Turk Revolution in Turkey in 1908 had a strong impact on the modern worldview.

Jadids gathered around their newspapers and magazines, new method schools, various libraries and reading rooms, and amateur theater troupes. Most of them were prominent artists of this period - poets and writers. They created a historically new national literature with their works. Literature went in sync with the events of the time. In the 1910s, the ideas of enlightenment and freedom became his central theme. The concepts of "nation" and "homeland" entered the literature. Enthusiasm for national poems increased. A new modern epic appeared, journalism (Behbudi, Fitrat, Munavvarkri, Mirmuhsin) developed, realistic prose was formed. That is why, after the independence of Uzbekistan, the literature of this period was rightfully called the Uzbek literature of the period of national renaissance [3].

Such a revival in literature took place at the same time in the cultural life of this period. Jadidlar brought a literal national theater into the life of the Uzbek people. With the establishment of the National Printing House, book printing began. Jadids, who got acquainted with the art of European polyphonic music, called for the reform of Uzbek traditional music styles as well. In 1919, the National (Old City) Department of the People's Conservatory of Turkestan was established on the initiative of the Jadids in the Old City part of Tashkent (now the building next to the “Turon” library). In this way, Jadids tried to raise the image of the nation through the means of art, to raise almost all types of art (in the relevant sections of the special volume “Republic of Uzbekistan” - Literature, Theater, Music, most of the representatives of Jadidchilik first of all religious education to young people along with, they put the issue of teaching secular subjects on the agenda. They reformed the educational methods and programs of Muslim schools and opened new schools. Behbudi, Munavvarqori, A. Burkhanov, A. Avloni, and others wrote and published textbooks for the New Usul schools (see New Usul schools).

During the Jadidism movement, their own press was formed. Jadids were published in Tashkent in 1905-1906 by “Taraqqi” (editor-Ismail Obiliy), “Khurshid” (editor- Munavvarqori), in 1907-1908 “Shuhrat” (editor-A. Avloni), “Asia” (editor-Ahmadjon Bektemirov), “Tujjor” (editor-Saidkarimboy Saidazimboy oglu), “Bukharai Sharif” (editor-Mirzo Jalal Yusufzoda) in Bukhara in 1912, “Turon” (editor-Ghiyas Makhsum Hosseini), in Samarkand in 1913 “Samarkand” (editor-M. Behbudi), “Sadoyi Turkistan” (editor-Ubaydulla Khojaev) in Tashkent, “Sadoyi Fargana” (editor-Obidjon Mahmudov) in Kokand and “Oyina” (editor - M.) in Samarkand in 1913-1915. Behbudi in Tashkent in 1915 published the magazine “Al-islah” (editor - son of Abdurahman Sadiq). Also, in 1917-1918, “Salvation” (editor-Munavvarqori), “Kengash” (editors-Ahmed Zakiy Walidiy and Munavvarqori), “Turon” (editors-M. Afandizoda, A. Avloni), “Ulug‘ Turkestan” (editor-Kabir Bakirov), “Shuroy Islam” (editor - Abdulla Battol), “Turk sozi” (editor-Temirbek Khudoyorkhanov), “Turk eli” (edited), “Hurriyat” in Samarkand (editors-Mardonqul Shahmuhammadzade, Akobir Shomansurov, Fitrat), “Tirik soz” (editor-Obidjon Mahmudov), “El Bayroghi” (editor - Bolat Soliev) and “Kengash” (editor - Hamza), “Yurt” (editor) newspapers in Kok - Ashurali Zahiri) magazines were published. The press was not satisfied with copying the words of the national language to its pages, but raised the issue of what to do first [4].

In 1909, “Jamiyati Khairiya” was established by the young intellectuals of Tashkent. The issue of training local youth to work in state courts, industrial and commercial spheres, and providing cultural and spiritual support to poor Muslims was raised. These were measures taken to prevent the nation from being absorbed into other nations.

During this period, the Jadids appeared as a social and political force. The people felt their protectors in them. Abduvahidqori Abduraufgoriev, who was elected as a member of the State Duma to be held in Petersburg from Syrdarya region, was tasked with submitting a 12-item petition from the residents of Tashkent, Shymkent and other places to the State Duma. Many social requirements were specified in this document. On February 20-June 3, 1907, Abduvahidqori met Muslim intellectuals such as Sadri Maqsudi (1879-1957), Musa Zorilloh, Alimardon Topchiboshev in Petersburg, and conveyed the pain of the people of Turkestan to the chairman of the Muslim faction, Biglov. However, Abduvahidqori was soon imprisoned and exiled to Tula.

While announcing the opinions of its representatives, the Jadid press showed that it is the “opener of the nation's consciousness” that “always awakens the people from the sleep of heedlessness” and prepared the people of Turkestan for free thinking and a great political struggle. During this period, such associations as “Erk”, “Turon”, “Teachers‘ Society” appeared. As Munavvarqori said, “All their hopes were

aimed at liberating the local population from national and religious restrictions and oppression during the revolution in Russia, equalizing their rights with Europeans, creating a wide opportunity to organize various schools and press works, as well as various societies.”

Jadids worked under the slogan “Freedom, equality and justice” during this period. Their 1916 the reaction to the incident of employment is very noteworthy. Recruitment - recruitment of Turkestans to work in the places where the First World War was going on was carried out in accordance with the decree of the White Tsar on June 25, 1916. This unexpected event was, first of all, contrary to the treaty of 1865. Second, according to General Kuropatkin (1848 - 1925), in Karaganda, “The population and the administration were completely unprepared for work outside the settlement, and such a hastily implemented event caused serious disturbances.” At such a difficult time for the population, one of the prominent representatives of the moderns, U. Khojaev (Chairman of the Turkistan Labor Recruitment Committee) and the nationalist rich Mirkomilboy Mirmo‘minboev, drew the attention of the Russian public to this issue and canceled the decree. they went to Petersburg. At the meeting of the State Duma held on December 13 and 15, 1916, it was recognized that the decree of Nicholas II of June 25 was adopted contrary to the circumstances specified in the legislation of the Russian Empire.

Until the decree was discussed in the Duma, several echelons were stopped in June-August by the Jadid movement. The attempts of the Jadids to return the workers came to fruition with the beginning of the February Revolution of 1917. This incident raised their reputation among the people. This situation indicated that the Jadids had already moved from enlightenment to political struggle [5].

In 1917, the Jadid movement entered a new stage. After the February revolution, the Uzbeks, Tatars and Kazakhs decided to unite and the “Shuroy Islamiya” society was established on the basis of the “Turon” association (the founders were Munavvarqori, Abduvahidqori Abduraufqoriev, U. Khojaev). 1917 This society, which started its work on March 14, sent propagandists to villages and cities, explained about freedom and equality, and gave information about elections. Its program was written by Munavvarqori. Jadids initiated the creation of the “Shuroy Islamiya” system. The movement to grant the status of autonomy to Turkestan turned into a struggle for the independence of Turkestan.

On September 1-7, 1920, the Congress of the Peoples of the East was convened in Baku. The decisions made at the congress played a certain role in the future fate of the people of Turkestan. Turkestan people like Munavvarqori, Turor Riskulov, Cholpon, Sapimkhan Tillakhonov, Rajab Muhamedov, Qudratilla Yunusov, Tashpolatbek Norbotabekov, Obidjon Mahmudov, Torakul Jonuzokov, Zayniddin Ghorri Nasriddinov, Haji Safo Joraboev, Ghozi Yunus. A total of 90 people from the

devotees of the nation participated. Anvar Pasha, who came from Turkey and was personally sent by Lenin himself, also took part in the congress. However, it became clear at the meetings that this congress was a taunt of the Bolsheviks against England. Therefore, after the congress, 40 delegates from Turkestan held a council among themselves and decided to intensify “propaganda against the Soviet government in Turkestan” and “raise a national uprising on the third anniversary of the October Revolution.” However, their plan was not fully realized.

Turkestan Jadids have created such groups as “Turon Kuchi”, “Turk Kuchi”, “Temur”, “Izchilar”, “Lochin”, whose activities cover the whole country and work on the basis of a program similar to the British scouting school program. In addition to high school education, crafts, and art, these groups are engaged in military exercises, and they began to appear as the main striking force of the Soviets. In 1920, the Soviet regime ended the activity of these groups.

After the Soviet rule was established in Turkestan by violence, some of the Jadids withdrew from active political life and engaged only in artistic creation (A. Burkhanov, A. Avloni, S. Ainiy). Some veterans worked in the cultural and educational branches of the Soviet authorities (U. Khojaev, Munavvargori, Hamza, S. Tursunhojaev, T. Norbotabekov).

Some Jadids continued to work in high state and government positions as “local communists” (Fayzulla Khojaev, Abdulkadir Muhiddinov, Nizomiddin Khojaev). Some veterans joined the ranks of the independence movement in Turkestan and emigrated abroad (Usmonkhoja Polathojaev, Sadriddinkhan Sharifhojaev, Abdulhamid Oripov, etc.) [6].

In conclusion, it is necessary to note the following.

1. Due to the fact that the production forces and development were lagging behind, and the socio-political, ideological and theoretical level of the people was not sufficiently in line with the requirements of the time, this struggle did not succeed as a united great force. Political and social disunity, “know yourself, ignore others” mood damaged the national mood and national unity.

2. The people of the country did not massively support the Jadidism movement. This movement did not go beyond spreading the ideas of enlightenment and culture among the people, remained confined within its narrow circle, could not rise to the level of a party of political struggle and could not attract the masses to a programmatic struggle against tyranny and tyranny.

3. Russian Bolsheviks skilfully took advantage of the fact that the movement of Jadids had not reached the level of theoretical and political perfection and split them into two. A group of Jadids, believing the false and empty promises of the Bolsheviks, went over to their side and joined the “Yosh Bukharalik” and “Yosh Khivalik” groups. As a result, the forces fighting for national freedom and

independence were weakened and disorganized. 1918 yil noyabrda Toshkentda Turkiston Sharq instituti tashkil qilindi, institut nizomida uning asosiy vazifalari qilib Turkiston mahalliy aholisi va qo‘shni mamlakatlar tilini yaxshi biladigan sharxshunos olimlar tayyorlashdir deb belgilab qo‘yilgan.

The Uzbek nation, which has a long history, despite social and political obstacles, like other nations of Central Asia, brought forward thinkers, great scientists, and left immortal masterpieces and thoughts to humanity in the field of science and spirituality.

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